

BUILDING IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS - LIVING AND ITS ROLE IN CHILDREN'S EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5136510>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th July 2021

Accepted: 20th July 2021

Online: 25th July 2021

KEY WORDS

*construction, pre-school
education, educator.*

ABSTRACT

*This article describes the role and advantages of building
in pre-school education and its upbringing.*

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Number of PD-4312 of May 8, 2019 "Concept of development of pre-school education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", December 29, 2016 PO-2707 "On measures to further improve the system of pre-school education in 2017-2021", PO "On measures to further improve the management of the system of pre-school education" dated September 30, 2017 -5198 Decree Number of PD-3261 of September 9, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of pre-school education", as well as Resolution Number of 1-m. of June 1 "On the development of pre-school children" The section "State requirements" provides for the solution of issues related to this area in government documents, such as the implementation of the State Curriculum of the pre-school educational institution "First step". In pre-school, it is important to play and teach children with the help of building materials. Games and lessons with the help of building materials in pre-school

education play an important role in the comprehensive education of the younger generation. Children's construction games are an integral part of role-playing games. In construction games, too, children reflect on the things around them, the activities of adults. The content of the construction games is created by the children themselves. Children often imitate the construction activities of adults, according to the Ministry of Education on 2018 they play the role of "construction worker". Children's construction games are a fun creative activity. In their games, they reflect their impressions of the construction of traffic, the labor of adults. Such games provide a wide range of opportunities to stimulate initiative in children, activate their thinking and movement activities. During interaction and play, children interact differently with each other. They share roles, help and consult each other in getting things done. There are many elements of movement in construction games that help children meet

their demands for movement. When a child begins to build something, he takes the building materials to the right place, places them on a table or floor, bends over, at which point his hands move actively, that is, he expends a certain amount of physical force. The small muscles of the hand develop well when playing with small building materials. As a result of playing construction games, children's observation increases, their interest in technology grows. They are also introduced to the structure of simple geometric shapes during play. The educational effect of construction games is that they reflect the ideological content of events and objects that children reflect.

In pre-school children, the skills of thinking such as analysis and synthesis, the ability to compare are still poorly developed. Games with the help of building materials develop children's thinking and creative abilities. Remembering and re-remembering what the educator has shown forces children to compare, analyze, and simulate things, to find similarities and differences, and not to scatter construction tasks, to be satisfied with a random conclusion, not only, but also teaches to behave in accordance with the purpose. Systematic construction of children's knowledge is not only a means of learning about the environment, but also a means of cultivating moral qualities. Children are constantly watching the new housing, schools, kindergartens, shops being built around them and hearing from the educator the care that our government is doing for the people. Specific examples of construction help children to understand that the Uzbek people how much loved their work. Through construction games, educator tries to rise children's diligence,

independence, responsibility for their work. The games and competitions dedicated to the aging of the children's community are in full swing. In the process of thinking and training, children learn to concentrate, to achieve the set goal with perseverance and perseverance, to show creative initiative on the basis of the acquired knowledge and skills. The family occupies a special place in the masculinity of making the mixture. Through these occupations, they learn the elementary appearance of things, the ability to use the details of construction in accordance with the purpose, and aging from a medical point of view. Pre-school children of pupil age try to age, only pick up the materials in the building kits with the flat side and pick them up or put them in each other's cotton. While educator taught children to build various things, it is reflected in the construction games of young children.

Necessary, conditions to be carried out the occupation and play with construction materials. It is necessary to create the necessary conditions. To do this, first of all, there must be enough construction materials in the group. According to the pattern, the children should not be limited in construction games, but should be distributed to everyone. Let children learn to use the materials which are need. When children begin to acquire the skills of aging, they are allowed to start digging for small wounds. It is necessary to use construction balls in occupations. Large construction materials are used on the plot of most kindergartens. It teaches children to build, to play as a group. The tables can be arranged differently during the lesson so that all the children in the group can master the construction techniques.

When doing the construction individually, the tables can be stacked in the usual order or in the shape of the letter P, if the children do one construction in groups, 2-3 tables should be combined and arranged in a row. During the session, children are shown the most basic methods of construction, so the session should not be long (no more than 10-12 minutes). It is advisable to conduct construction classes in the first half of the school year. The purpose of the exercise is to demonstrate all the methods of construction: to demonstrate and explain in action all the methods of construction, to show a ready-made model and to analyze the elements that go into it. As an example, use a

prefabricated building that shows what can be made from building materials. Demonstrate some of the details of construction so that children can learn how to build a building (how to cover the top of a high foundation, how to replace one detail with another, how to widen a plane, etc.). Invite the children to continue some part of the construction being done by the educator. To give an idea about the object to be built, for example, to determine the size (big or small) of the construction, while saying that the construction is suitable for toys. Children should be provided with the necessary conditions and materials to teach them to be creative.

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